

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

This issue is a "mixed one": the first three contributions "A Framework to Evaluate Interface Suitability for a Given Scenario of Textual Information Retrieval" (by C. Bonnel et al) , "Nondeterministic Query Algorithms" (by Alina Vasilieva and Rusins Freivalds) and "Descriptive Complexity of Ambiguity in Symmetric Difference NFAs" (by Lynette van Zijl and Jaco Geldenhuys), have been submitted and reviewed as usually by the members of our editorial board, the other five papers are extended and peer-reviewed versions of outstanding papers originally presented at the "4th International Workshop on Intelligent, Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing" (IMIS 2010), February 15-18, 2010, at Krakow, Poland. The guest editor of this "mini special issue" was Ilun You from the Korean Bible University, Korea. We thank Prof. You for the effort he put into the preparation of this part of the current issue.

Just a sneak preview before it is more widely announced: the three institutions that have so far sponsored J.UCS will be joined by a number of additional ones: two from Germany, one from USA and one from Asia, and possibly also one from Australia and Canada, each. This will allow J.UCS even in times of tighter budget to maintain its policy of free submission and open access. If your institution would be interested in joining what will be called "J.UCS Consortium" and will be listed with its member on the future www.jucs.org page, let me know so we can discuss details!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

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